

fragments were observed at m/z 154/156 and 226 (Scheme 2). The base peak interestingly was observed at m/z 10³ which could originate from a hydrogen rearranged ion possessing structure 10. This rearrangement found corroboration from the fact that mass spectra of 4 and 1 had many ions in common. The envisaged loss of two hydrogens from M^+ led to an ion 9, which further fragmented in the manner as found for the photoproduct 5. The structure of 5 was deduced as follows. The mass spectroscopic data showed that its formation involved the loss of two mass units from 1 and RDA fragments were present at m/z 154/156 and 224. The molecular ion (M^+ , 378/380) here was found to be the base peak. A comparison of the pmr spectra of 1 and 5 reveals that the region between δ 7.8–7.95 (H_a , H_b) integrating for two protons for 1 had only one proton in the spectrum of 5 and the singlet at δ 5.06 ($2 \times H$) in the former was replaced by a singlet at δ 6.32 ($1 \times H$) in the latter. It was suggestive enough that in the photoconversion 1 \rightarrow 5, it is only H_a , or H_b , (both are chemically equivalent) and o - $CH_2C_6H_4R$ participated. A DDQ treatment of 4 in refluxing benzene provided 5.

The photolysis of 2 ($R=Cl$) also furnished two compounds (6 and 7). But 3 under the same conditions gave only 8. All our attempts to isolate a dihydro derivative (corresponding to 4 or 6) during photolysis of 3 proved abortive, though no particular reason for such behaviour can be assigned.

The molecular changes and cyclodehydrogenations involved in the photoreactions of the benzopyrans (1–3) may be explained in terms of the proximity of 3-benzyloxy group to $C=O$ of the pyrone moiety. Under the photolytic conditions, the excited $C=O$ abstracts a hydrogen from 3- O - CH_2 -, through a six-membered transition state, yielding a 1,4-diradical⁴ which then ends up in products (4–8).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Beckman IR-20, NMR Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz, $CDCl_3$, TMS internal standard) and JNM FX-100 FT, JMS-D-300S spectrometers were used. Petroleum ether used refer to the fraction having b.p. 60–80°.

The 3-benzyloxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyrans (1–3) were prepared starting from 5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone, C_6H_5CHO and NaOH, followed by cyclisation ($NaOH/H_2O_2$)⁵ and benzylation ($ClCH_2C_6H_4-R/K_2CO_3/acetone$).

Photolysis of benzopyrans: The benzopyran (1; 1.10 g) dissolved in thiophene-free benzene (200 ml) was photolysed (90 min) in a water-cooled pyrex glass immersion well with 200 W Hg vapour lamp. The dark yellow photolysate on evaporation (reduced pressure) and column chromatography on silica gel (30 g) with eluent benzene-petroleum

ether 7 : 3 and 4 : 1 gave 4 and 5 respectively. The compounds were purified through silica gel column (C_6H_6 -petroleum ether, 1 : 1) chromatography followed by preparative tlc (benzene-EtOAc, 98 : 2).

Dehydrogenation of 4: A benzene solution of 4 (0.1 g) was refluxed with DDQ (0.1 g) for 1 h. The resulting solution was percolated through a column of neutral Al_2O_3 and eluted with benzene to provide a solid, m.p. 230–31° (remained undepressed when mixed with 5).

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Lead Tetraacetate Oxidation of Steroidal Hydroxyketoximes

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Manuscript received 28 November 1989, revised 20 June 1990, accepted 3 July 1990

IN continuation of our previous studies¹, we report here the lead(IV) acetate oxidation of steroidal hydroxyketoximes (1–3). The reaction of 3 β ,5-hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one-oxime (1)² afforded 3 β -acetoxycholest-4-en-6-one (4)³, 3 β -acetoxy-5-hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one (5)⁴ and 3 β ,5-hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-*N*-acetate (6). Under similar reaction conditions, 3 β -acetoxy-5-hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one-oxime (2)⁴ furnished compounds 4, 5 and 3 β -acetoxy-5-hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-*N*-acetate (7). 3 β -Chloro-5-hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one oxime (3)⁴ when treated with lead(IV) acetate yielded β -chlorocholest-4-en-6-one (8)⁵, 3 β -chloro-5-hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one-7 α -acetate (9) and 3 β -chloro-5-hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-*N*-acetate (10). Structures of the compounds were supported by elemental analysis and spectral data (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4–10*

Compd. no.	Mol. formula	Solvent of elution pet. ether- ether	M.p. °C	Yield %	IR (KBr/Nujol) ν_{\max} cm^{-1}	$\delta^{\#}$
4	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_2$	20 : 1	106 ^a	15	1 740 (CH_2COO), 1 640 (C=O), 1 625 (C=C), 1 460, 1 380, 1 260, 1 040 (C-O)	5.4 (brs, C_4 -vinyllic), 4.5 (mc, $W_{1/2}$ 18 Hz, $\text{C}3\alpha\text{-H}$), 2.0 (s, CH_2COO)
5	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_4$	10 : 1	238 ^b	12.5	3 350 (OH), 1 710 (C=O), 1 460, 1 370, 1 280, 1 160, 1 040 (C-O)	4.02 (mc, $W_{1/2}$ 18 Hz, $\text{C}3\alpha\text{-H}$), 2.15 (s, OH), 2.1 (s, CH_2COO)
6	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_4\text{N}$	4 : 1	166 ^a	10	3 350 (OH), 1 725 (CH_2COO), 1 680 (C=N), 1 470, 1 380, 1 240, 1 040 (C-O)	3.8 (mc, $W_{1/2}$ 16 Hz, $\text{C}3\alpha\text{-H}$), 2.15 (s, OH), 1.95 (s, CH_2COO)
7	$\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{51}\text{O}_5\text{N}$	5 : 1	Oil	10	3 400 (OH), 1 735, 1 715 ($2 \times \text{CH}_2\text{COO}$), 1 660 (C=N), 1 460, 1 370, 1 240, 1 060 (C-O)	4.45 (mc, $W_{1/2}$ 16 Hz, $\text{C}3\alpha\text{-H}$), 2.2 (s, OH), 2.1, 2.0 (s, $2 \times \text{CH}_2\text{COO}$)
8	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{44}\text{OCl}$	16 : 1	164 ^c	12.5	1 680 (C-O), 1 625 (C=C), 760 (C-Cl)	4.8 (brs, $\text{C}4$ -vinyllic), 3.8 (mc, $W_{1/2}$ 16 Hz, $\text{C}3\alpha\text{-H}$)
9	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{47}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	10 : 1	87 ^a	10	3 500 (OH), 1 735 (CH_2COO), 1 690 (C=O), 1 460, 1 380, 1 260, 1 030 (C-O), 800 (C-Cl)	4.7 (brs, $\text{C}7\beta\text{-H}$), 3.4 (mc, $W_{1/2}$ 16 Hz, $\text{C}3\alpha\text{-H}$), 2.30 (s, OH), 2.05 (s, CH_2COO)
10	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_5\text{NCl}$	5 : 1	Oil	7	3 400 (OH), 1 745 (CH_2COO), 1 660, (C=N), 1 460, 1 370, 1 210, 1 060 (C-O), 760 (C-Cl)	3.4 (mc, $W_{1/2}$ 16 Hz, $\text{C}3\alpha\text{-H}$), 2.15 (s, OH), 1.95 (s, CH_2COO)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and/or N analyses.

**Solvent of crystallisation: ^amethanol, ^bmethanol-acetone, ^cacetone, ^dpetroleum ether.

[#]Angular and side chain methyl protons appeared between 0.70 and 1.20.

Experimental

All melting points were determined on Kofler's block apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP3-100 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian A-60D instrument using TMS as internal standard.

Reaction of 3β,5-hydroxy-5α-cholestan-6-one-oxime with lead(IV) acetate. General procedure: Lead(IV) acetate (2.0 g) was added portionwise to a stirred solution of 3β,5-hydroxy-5α-cholestan-6-one-oxime (1; 2.0 g) in dry benzene (40 ml) and glacial acetic acid (20 ml). The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 h and then solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was taken up in ether and the ethereal layer was washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvent gave an oil which was chromatographed over silica gel

(40 g). Elution with petroleum ether-ether in different solvent ratios gave different products (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. S. A. A. Zaidi, Chairman, Department of Chemistry for facilities and to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial support to one of them (R.K.P.).

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steroidal diols (1-3)² with lead(IV) acetate in dry benzene and a catalytic amount of iodine.

Ir spectra of the 6β,19-oxido-5-hydroxy-5α-cholestanes (4-6) exhibited characteristic bands at 3 460-3 430 cm⁻¹ (OH), 2 950-2 940s (CH) and 1 240-1 225 cm⁻¹ (epoxide linkage). The ¹H nmr spectra revealed C-6 proton at δ 5.3-5.2, C-3 proton at δ 4.7-3.4 and 19 C-H_a protons at δ 4.2-4.1. The mass spectral fragmentations (Scheme 1) of 4-6 were as anticipated³, thus supporting the assigned structures of the compounds.

Scheme 1

Synthesis of 6β,19-Oxido-steroids

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Manuscript received 28 November 1989, accepted 19 June 1990

THERE a number of reports¹ on the synthesis of 6β,19-oxidosteroids from steroidal bromohydrins and epoxides. Here, we report the synthesis of 3β-substituted-6β,19-oxido-5-hydroxy-5α-cholestane derivatives (4-6) by the reaction of

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr/nujol) were determined on a Pye-Unicam SP3-100 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A 60 instrument (60 Hz) with Me₄Si as the internal standard and mass spectra on a JeOL-D 300 spectrometer at 70 eV. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used as drying agent.

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4-6*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	ν _{max} cm ⁻¹	δ**
4	135	41	C ₂₇ H ₄₄ O ₂ Cl	3 430 (OH), 2 950 (CH), 1 240 (epoxide linkage), 730 (C-Cl)	5.3 (1H, br s, C6-αH), 4.1 (2H, br s, C19-H _a), 3.5 (1H, mc, W _{1/2} 16 Hz, C3-αH) 2.1 (1H, s, C5-αOH)
5	101	40	C ₂₉ H ₄₆ O ₄	3 440 (OH), 2 940 (CH), 1 725, 1 240 (CH ₃ COO), 1 225 (epoxide linkage)	5.2 (1H, br s, C6-αH), 4.2 (2H, br s, C19-H _a), 4.7 (1H, mc, W _{1/2} 18 Hz, C3-αH), 2.2 (1H, s, C5-αOH), 2.0 (3H, s, CH ₃ COO)
6	Oil	40	C ₂₇ H ₄₄ O ₂	3 460-3 400 (OH), 2 950 (CH), 1 235 (epoxide linkage)	5.3 (1H, br s, C6-αH), 4.2 (2H, br s, C19-H _a), 3.4 (1H, mc, W _{1/2} 18 Hz, C3-αH), 2.1 (1H, s, C5-αOH)

*All compounds showed satisfactory C and H analyses.

**Angular and side-chain methyl protons appeared at δ 0.95-0.69.